

Monitoring cyanobacteria blooms with complementary measurements – a similar story told using high-throughput imaging, optical sensors, light microscopy, and satellite-based methods

Kaisa Kraft^{a,*}, Lumi Haraguchi^a, Heidi Hällfors^a, Sanna Suikkanen^b, Pasi Ylöstalo^a, Sami Kielosto^a, Annaliina Skyttä^a, Lauri Laakso^{c,d}, Martti Honkanen^c, Mati Kahru^e, Jukka Seppälä^a

^a Finnish Environment Institute Syke, Research Infrastructure, Helsinki, Finland

^b Finnish Environment Institute Syke, Marine and Freshwater Solutions, Helsinki, Finland

^c Finnish Meteorological Institute, Helsinki, Finland

^d Atmospheric Chemistry Research Group, Chemical Resource Beneficiation, North-West University, Potchefstroom, South Africa

^e Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California, San Diego, La Jolla, CA 92093, USA

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Baltic sea
Cyanobacteria bloom
IFCB
Method comparison

ABSTRACT

Several methods to monitor cyanobacteria exist, based partly on characteristics that differentiate cyanobacteria from other phytoplankton, such as pigmentation and morphology. However, it is not certain whether all methods give similar insights into the development and properties of a cyanobacterial bloom. It is important to understand the level of consistency of measurements, especially in the case of novel methods. In situ imaging flow cytometry provides community composition information at high frequency but has been little used for filamentous bloom-forming cyanobacteria. To understand if different methods agree, we compared multi-year biomass data collected with Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB), CytoSense (CS), phycocyanin (PC) and chlorophyll (Chl) *a* fluorescence, and turbidity sensors, light microscopy, and satellite-based Frequency of Cyanobacteria Accumulations (FCA). Continuous high-throughput data was recorded at Utö Atmospheric and Marine Research Station in the Baltic Sea during summers 2018–2022, along with samples for light microscopy and adjacent satellite observations. The IFCB cyanobacteria biomass pattern most closely resembled those of CS and PC fluorescence. IFCB also described the blooms similarly to FCA, and to some extent to turbidity, but differed from Chl *a* fluorescence. IFCB and light microscopy agreed on the bloom development and species composition but differed concerning exact biomass. Our study demonstrates that both IFCB and CS are suitable for studying filamentous cyanobacteria and that in situ imaging flow cytometry provides valuable support for cyanobacteria monitoring by yielding detailed high-frequency taxon-specific information. Still, the best overall coverage of rapid biological processes such as bloom development is achieved with the parallel use of multiple observation techniques.

1. Introduction

Phytoplankton, including cyanobacteria, are responsible for most of the primary production of the seas, have fast turnover rates, and respond rapidly to changes in environmental conditions. Investigation of phytoplankton long-term trends relies on data from monitoring programs, often with rather infrequent sampling with monthly or even more sparse intervals. Monitoring stations with weekly sampling are

rare, and even when they exist, this resolution often misses short biomass peaks while large blooms are easily either under- or over-estimated (Sonnet et al., 2024). The extent of sampling campaigns is restricted by the labor-intensive light microscopy analysis, with one sample taking up to a full day to analyze. Remote sensing and bio-optical sensors are used to complement the sparse sampling interval, but they produce only bulk information, with taxon-specific methods being less common (Bertone et al., 2018; Lombard et al., 2019; Kramer et al.,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: kaisa.kraft@syke.fi (K. Kraft), lumi.haraguchi@syke.fi (L. Haraguchi), heidi.hallfors@syke.fi (H. Hällfors), sanna.suikkanen@syke.fi (S. Suikkanen), pasi.ylostalo@syke.fi (P. Ylöstalo), sami.kielosto@syke.fi (S. Kielosto), annaliina.skytta@syke.fi (A. Skyttä), lauri.laakso@fmi.fi (L. Laakso), martti.honkanen@fmi.fi (M. Honkanen), mkahru@ucsd.edu (M. Kahru), jukka.seppala@syke.fi (J. Seppälä).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2025.102865>

Received 21 November 2024; Received in revised form 20 March 2025; Accepted 14 April 2025

Available online 24 April 2025

1568-9883/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

2022). Automated observation technologies for phytoplankton have been identified as a new source of input to national and international databases, serving the needs of both monitoring and research purposes (Muller-Karger et al., 2018). Our paper examines how these different methods compare in describing the development of filamentous cyanobacteria blooms in the Baltic Sea.

Cyanobacteria occur from freshwater to marine environments, but blooms are more common in freshwater and brackish systems (Huisman et al., 2018). During the past decade, there has been a growing global concern about the development of cyanobacteria blooms (e.g., O'Neil et al., 2012; Paerl et al., 2018; Wells et al., 2020). Many cyanobacteria species can fix atmospheric nitrogen (N_2), giving them an advantage in nitrogen-depleted conditions, enabling bloom formation and contributing new nitrogen to the system (Zehr and Capone, 2020; Marcarelli et al., 2022). Although cyanobacteria blooms, in general, are a natural phenomenon, there is an indication of increasing frequency and magnitude due to eutrophication, as well as climate and other anthropogenic changes (Huisman et al., 2018; Wells et al., 2020, and references therein). Cyanobacteria blooms may have an impact on drinking water production, human and animal health, recreational use, as well as ecosystem functioning through toxicity. Furthermore, nontoxic blooms are considered a nuisance for recreational use and cause oxygen depletion through high biomass accumulation, resulting in a high amount of decomposing matter (Huisman et al., 2018). Understanding the dynamics and driving factors of cyanobacteria blooms is of global importance. This is the case in the Baltic Sea, where (harmful and) potentially toxic filamentous cyanobacteria blooms occur annually, with the bloom season starting sometime in June-August when the biomass rises over $200 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Wasmund et al., 1997).

There are multiple methods available for monitoring cyanobacteria, from classical cell enumeration using light microscopy to satellite remote sensing, and from molecular tools to high-throughput bio-optical sensors and imaging flow cytometry (de Figueiredo, 2024). Technological developments in recent decades have increased the use of high-throughput methods for phytoplankton detection, one frequently used emerging method being imaging flow cytometry (Lombard et al., 2019). In situ imaging flow cytometers allow continuous monitoring of the phytoplankton community with high-frequency sampling, producing information on a time scale needed to follow the fast turnover rates and bloom phenology of phytoplankton. Imaging flow cytometry platforms are also recognized as having potential within monitoring frameworks but are still rather little used, at least on a European scale (Korpinen et al., 2022).

Common bloom-forming filamentous cyanobacteria have a morphology that is distinguishable in imaging flow cytometry images, often to genus level (Mirasbekov et al., 2021; Kraft et al., 2022). The three most common imaging flow cytometers for phytoplankton are the benchtop device FlowCam (Sieracki et al., 1998) and the in situ instruments IFCB and CytoSense (CS). With IFCB and FlowCam, quantification is done through images, while with CS, this is achieved through the optical fingerprints of each particle, with a subset of images being taken as additional information to help identify different particle populations. FlowCam has been proven appropriate for the enumeration of cyanobacteria (Graham et al., 2018; Hrycik et al., 2019). However, as far as the authors are aware, only two publications have used CS (van Dijk et al., 2010; Doppler et al., 2022) and another two have used IFCB (Kraft et al., 2021; Dugenne et al., 2023) to study filamentous cyanobacteria, and only Kraft et al. (2021) and Doppler et al. (2022) have focused on the applicability.

Cyanobacteria have a unique pigment composition with their special light-harvesting complexes, phycobilisomes (Watanabe and Ikeuchi, 2013). The specific pigment composition varies by species. The phycobilisomes always comprise the components phycocyanin (PC) and allophycocyanin (APC), and, depending on species, additional phycoerythrin (PE) or phycoerythrocyanin (PEC) components may be present (Watanabe and Ikeuchi, 2013). Due to their characteristic

pigments with specific fluorescing properties, cyanobacteria can be detected with optical sensors for PE and PC fluorescence (Bertone et al., 2018), including a CS equipped with a laser exiting in the orange to the red wavelengths. Numerous publications also show that the abundance of cyanobacteria can be assessed with remote sensing of PC (review by Ogashawara, 2020). When forming mass occurrences, cyanobacteria tend to form surface accumulations visible in satellite images. The accumulations can be determined from satellite data based on the detection of water turbidity using ocean color sensors. This is the method used in Frequency of Cyanobacteria Accumulations (FCA), a technique that can successfully detect blooms of filamentous cyanobacteria (Kahru et al., 2007; Kahru and Elmgren, 2014).

To gain a comprehensive understanding of cyanobacteria blooms and the cause-and-effect relationships that trigger bloom formation, observations need to be based on more than one technology. Different methods have different strengths and weaknesses: light microscopy samples are taken at infrequent intervals and the analysis is time-consuming, but the resulting data has a high taxonomic resolution; in situ imaging requires expensive equipment and special skills, but produces temporally frequent taxonomical time-series data; optical measurements lack taxonomic resolution, but are relatively inexpensive and produce temporally frequent time-series data; and satellite observations depend on clear skies and are not very frequently updated (often from daily interval upwards), but have extensive spatial coverage. Thus, a suite of methods can best describe the development of blooms in different temporal and spatial scales, assuming the information they provide is consistent and combinable. Therefore, the understanding of how different methods with different temporal and spatial scales and taxonomic resolution correspond is important, especially in the case of novel methods. The importance of intercalibration and understanding how different methods compare to each other has also been identified in the field of harmful algal blooms (Stauffer et al., 2019). Assessing the possibilities that novel in situ observational methods bring regarding cyanobacteria is of high interest from a global perspective (see e.g., Huisman et al., 2018, and references therein).

Classical light microscopy is the method that other approaches for cyanobacteria detection are most commonly compared to (e.g., Briant et al., 2008; Hrycik et al., 2019; Thomson-Laing et al., 2020; Kraft et al., 2021; Karlson et al., 2022), and e.g. Seppälä et al. (2007) and Yang et al. (2019) have compared bio-optical sensors to one another. Only a few studies are comparing multiple observation methods for cyanobacteria (Bertani et al., 2017), and studies utilizing novel in situ imaging flow cytometry methods are scarce (van Dijk et al., 2010; Kraft et al., 2021; Doppler et al., 2022; Dugenne et al., 2023), with only Kraft et al. (2021) and Doppler et al. (2022) concentrating on comparability.

Wider comparisons provide important information on how the data obtained from the new methods compares to each other and more classical approaches. Although comprehensive comparisons for cyanobacteria are scarce, a recent study by Kramer et al. (2024) focused on analyzing the correspondence of different emerging methods concerning other phytoplankton groups. They assessed the phytoplankton community composition described by imaging and regular flow cytometry, eDNA and pigment-based methods, finding similarities between pigments and IFCB data with multiple taxonomic groups but with low or non-existent statistical significance. Their study demonstrates that while similarities between methods exist, it may be difficult, when using data from multiple locations, to have statistically significant relationships between observation methods.

In this study, we assess how comparable the results obtained from the IFCB are to another high-throughput in situ phytoplankton instrument, CS, in situ bulk bio-optical sensors (chlorophyll (Chl) *a* and PC fluorescence, turbidity), classical light microscopy, and satellite-derived FCA. The suite of methods provided an interesting setting to see how IFCB relates to 1) methods with different spatial and temporal resolutions (light microscopy and FCA), 2) a similar but slightly different instrument for phytoplankton community characterization (CS), and 3)

bio-optical sensors that have high temporal resolution but provide only bulk information of the community (Chl *a* and PC fluorescence, turbidity). To our knowledge, this is the first time in situ imaging flow cytometry has been compared this widely for the detection of filamentous cyanobacteria and the first time the results of IFCB and CS have been compared.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sampling station

The data was collected in June–August 2018, 2020, 2021, and 2022 at the Utö Atmospheric and Marine Research Station located on the small island of Utö in the southern part of the Archipelago Sea, Baltic Sea (59°46.84' N, 21°22.13' E, Fig. 1). The location is near the open Northern Baltic Proper and provides facilities for maintaining a wide range of autonomous and multidisciplinary observations (Laakso et al., 2018). The sampling station is part of the Joint European Research Infrastructure network for Coastal Observatories (JERICO-RI; Puillat et al., 2016) and the Finnish Marine Research Infrastructure (FINMARI). Numerous meteorological and atmospheric variables are measured at Utö Island within one kilometer from the water sampling site (Fig. 1; Laakso et al., 2018; Appendix A, Honkanen et al., 2024).

Sea water is pumped continuously from 250 m offshore using an underwater pump (Grundfos SP3A-9N) and distributed through several flow-through channels to different sensors inside the station building (Fig. 1; Honkanen et al., 2024). The pump is located on the seabed at 23 m depth, and water is taken using a floating sampling inlet at a depth of 4.5 m, representing the mixed near-surface layer. Water is pumped at a rate of 50–60 L min⁻¹ through a 50 mm black polyethylene pipe on the seabed, thus, the residence time is ~5–6 min. The pumping has little

effect on the filamentous cyanobacteria filament length and concentrations (Kraft et al., 2021). Parameters to be included in this study were filamentous cyanobacteria biomass from IFCB, CS, and light microscopy (also taxon-specific except for CS), total community biomass from IFCB, PC fluorescence from fluorometer and CS, Chl *a* fluorescence, turbidity, and FCA. The observations were sampled from the flow-through system, except for FCA, which is a satellite-based parameter (Table 1).

2.2. Sensor-based flow-through observations

Temperature and salinity were measured with a thermosalinograph (SBE45MicroTSG, Sea-Bird Scientific). Because the temperature of the sample water changes slightly as it flows through the sampling tube, a temperature correction was made according to Honkanen et al. (2021, 2024).

Chl *a* fluorescence and turbidity were measured continuously with a Wetlabs ECO FLNTU fluorometer (Sea-Bird Scientific) in the flow-through system. The sensor was calibrated using algal cultures for Chl *a* and with formazin for turbidity. Water samples to measure extracted Chl *a* were taken from the flow-through system and analyzed according to HELCOM (2016). Chl *a* fluorescence results were adjusted to represent Chl *a* concentrations. This conversion was done by using a linear relationship ($r^2 = 0.76$, $n = 159$, Supplementary figure 1).

PC fluorescence was measured with a MicroFlu-Blue fluorometer (TriOS Mess- und Datentechnik GmbH). The sensor has an excitation waveband at 620 nm and detects emission at 655 nm. It is relatively insensitive to interference from Chl *a* fluorescence (Seppälä et al., 2007). To allow between-year comparison of readings, the sensor was calibrated once a year with reference sensors and a cyanobacteria culture (*Synechococcus* sp., strain TV65, collected at Tvärminne, prior to 1992, by G. & S. Hällfors, and provided by the FINMARI Culture

Fig. 1. Satellite image of the northern Baltic Sea (left), 15.7.2018, with extensive cyanobacteria blooms (the green swirls). The location of the study site at Utö is indicated by the red dot (left). The area of the satellite image in the Baltic Sea is indicated by the black square (bottom middle). The measurement site in Utö with the location of the pump, water intake, and measurement cabin (top right). The flow-through system inside the measurement cabin with the sensors connected to (bottom right). Image source: left: Tarkka, Syke (Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data); bottom middle: Esri, DeLorme, HERE, MapmyIndia, modified with QGIS; top right: Simo-Matti Siiriä, FMI, from Honkanen et al. (2024) 10.5194/bg-21-4341-2024; bottom right: Katri Kuuppo, FINMARI, <https://www.finmari-infrastructure.fi/facilities/field-stations/uto-fmi/>.

Table 1
Details of the different parameters.

Parameter	Taxa included	Obs. from	Years	Operating principle	Obs. n
IFCB filam cyanobacteria	<i>Aphanizomenon</i> spp., <i>Dolichospermum</i> spp., <i>Nodularia</i> spp.	flow-through	All	imaging	6737
IFCB total community	All images in sample	flow-through	All	imaging	6737
CS cyanobacteria	PC containing cyanobacteria, excluding pico-sized	flow-through	2021	optical profile	1832
Light microscopy	<i>Aphanizomenon</i> spp., <i>Dolichospermum</i> spp., <i>Nodularia</i> spp., Filam cyanobacteria = sum of the three taxa	flow-through	All, excl 2020	manual identification and enumeration	20
PC fluorescence	All PC containing taxa	flow-through	All	bulk optical	6842
PC fluorescence from CS	PC containing cyanobacteria, excluding pico-sized	flow-through	2021	bulk optical of the selected group of optical profiles	1832
Chl <i>a</i> fluorescence	All Chl <i>a</i> containing taxa	flow-through	All	bulk optical	7564
Turbidity	Everything causing turbidity	flow-through	All, excl 2021	bulk optical	5388
FCA	Everything causing turbidity	satellite	All	detection of turbid water	83

The flow-through intake is at a 4.5 m depth; All years include 2018, 2020, 2021, 2022.

Collection/Syke Marine Research Laboratory and Tvärminne Zoological Station). However, due to the lack of truly traceable calibration, the results are presented as relative fluorescence units. The calibration uses purified water in the determination of offset, while readings on site are somewhat affected by organic matter and the flow cap of the instrument. Therefore, we made a baseline correction by manually subtracting an annual baseline of the PC fluorescence readings. This was determined for a period when bloom-forming filamentous cyanobacteria were absent based on IFCB.

Once a day, the sensors, their flow caps, and the hoses connecting them were automatically cleaned with detergent (Triton X-100). In addition, the sensors were cleaned manually every week.

2.3. Imaging FlowCytobot, IFCB

The IFCB was used in a continuous mode, a new sample run starting immediately after the previous one finished. The instrument processed a 5-mL sample every ~20 min, except for gaps caused by short-term events such as power loss or maintenance of the flow-through system. The imaged particles ranged in size from single cells with a diameter of ~5 μm to cyanobacteria with a filament length of ~300 μm . A Chl *a* trigger was used (a red diode laser with 636 nm and 4.5 mW, PMT band 680 nm) to reduce the amount of imaged detritus and other non-living material. To prevent the instrument from clogging a 150 μm mesh was used at the inlet. A more detailed description is provided by Kraft et al. (2021).

The image data were classified with the method described by Kraft

Fig. 2. The different Baltic Sea bloom-forming filamentous cyanobacteria captured with IFCB (images without the scale bar) and CS (images with the scale bar). *Aphanizomenon* bundles (A, B) and single filaments (C, D), *Nodularia* single filaments (E, F) and bigger aggregates and coils (G, H), *Dolichospermum* coils (I, L) and single filaments (J, K).

et al. (2022) but using an updated version of the classifier. In short, the classification was done using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) algorithm, trained using a manually labeled (i.e., identified by a group of phytoplankton researchers) set of images. The image classification was done with Python using Resnet-18 as a backbone architecture trained with ImageNet and finetuned with a local image dataset (for details see Kraft et al., 2022). The computations were run in Puhti supercomputing environment, provided by the Finnish IT Center for Science (CSC).

The classifier contained 103 classes. Filamentous cyanobacteria were classified into five separate classes. The class *Aphanizomenon* (Fig. 2A, C) contains all *Aphanizomenon* species, but in Utö it comprises mainly *A. flosaquae*. *Dolichospermum* has two separate classes (“straight” (Fig. 2J) and “coiled” (Fig. 2I) forms) that encompass all *Dolichospermum* species (and to a lesser degree also similar taxa, such as *Anabaenopsis*, *Cronbergia*, and *Anabaena* species). The division into two *Dolichospermum* classes is necessary to facilitate the transformation of the biovolumes of coiled filaments into more realistic ones (see details in the next section and Kraft et al., 2021). The *Nodularia* class contains all potential *Nodularia* species, in Utö mainly the species *Nodularia spumigena*. Similarly to *Dolichospermum*, *Nodularia* is split into “straight” (Fig. 2F) and “coiled” (Fig. 2G) forms. The “straight” and “coiled” forms were joined after correction of the “coiled” biovolumes. Hence, from here onwards, the filamentous cyanobacteria from IFCB data are referred to as *Aphanizomenon*, *Dolichospermum*, and *Nodularia*.

Coiled cyanobacterial filaments often form closed loops (Fig. 2G, H, I, L), the empty center of which is incorrectly interpreted as cell content by the biovolume calculation algorithm. Consequently, the biovolume extracted during the image processing method overestimated the biovolumes of such filaments. For the class *Dolichospermum* “coiled”, the biovolume was calculated based on a conversion factor described in Kraft et al. (2021). The conversion factor was drawn based on manual cell counts of 158 filaments and their algorithm-based biovolumes. The conversion factor was calculated by fitting a regression line of a linear model using an intercept of zero to prevent conversion from producing negative biovolumes. After using the slope factor of the linear model for converting the *Dolichospermum* “coiled” biovolumes, the two *Dolichospermum* categories (i.e., “straight” and “coiled”) were merged.

For the class *Nodularia*, a similar analysis was done by measuring the filament length and calculating the biovolume based on that, using the biovolume of a 12 μm wide filament from Olenina et al. (2006). The rationale for using this predetermined biovolume was that *Nodularia* filament width can be difficult to determine due to the greatly varying focal points of the coils. For *Nodularia*, the variation in biovolumes was too large to use only one conversion factor. Therefore, the manually measured coiled *Nodularia* data were split into two groups based on IFCB biovolume, and a linear model was fitted for the observations below a threshold. The threshold value was chosen based on visual inspection of the biovolumes and by testing which threshold would give the best fit for the model. A threshold of 200 000 μm^3 was chosen, resulting in $n = 209$ for data $< 200\,000\ \mu\text{m}^3$ and $n = 48$ for data $> 200\,000\ \mu\text{m}^3$. A conversion factor of 1/2.1465 was drawn from the model and used to convert all the biovolumes $< 200\,000\ \mu\text{m}^3$. IFCB biovolumes $> 200\,000\ \mu\text{m}^3$ were chosen to be replaced by a median (36,431 μm^3) of the manual measurements of the data with IFCB biovolumes $> 200\,000\ \mu\text{m}^3$, since it was infeasible to try to fit the data into a linear model.

The trigger for image taking is always followed by a short “dead time”, making the volume observed smaller than the initial sample volume, therefore, the volume of the actual sample observed was considered. It was done by calculating the volume from the flow rate and the sample runtime reduced by the time when the particles may have passed through without being detected (Olson and Sosik, 2007). Pixel-based biovolumes were produced for each image according to the distance map method of Moberg and Sosik (2012). For converting pixel-based biovolumes to micrometer-based biovolumes, a conversion factor of 3.5 pixels per micrometer was determined using 6 μm standard beads (AlignFlow Plus, Molecular Probes, Inc.). The thus-acquired

micrometer-based biovolumes were then converted to biomass ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), assuming a plasma density of 1 g cm^{-3} according to CEN (2015). For a more detailed description of the method, see Kraft et al. (2021). The data were averaged over one hour, and the hourly results were used for all other analyzes, except for the comparison with FCA, for which IFCB data were averaged for a 5-day period corresponding to the FCA periods.

2.4. CytoSense, CS

A pulse-shape recorder flow cytometer, CytoSense (Cytobuoy, NL), was used to characterize the phytoplankton community during summer 2021. The instrument has a large flow cell, allowing the analysis of a broad size range of organisms ($< 1\text{--}800\ \mu\text{m}$) found in phytoplankton communities (Dubelaar et al., 1999). The instrument used in this study is equipped with two lasers (488 and 594 nm) and detectors for forward and sideward scatter and fluorescence at 502–538, 553–577, 604–644, and 668–726 nm, corresponding to fluorescein isothiocyanate dyes, PE, PC and Chl *a*, respectively. Each sensor records the optical features of a particle passing through the laser beam, and the sensor-specific information is stored, generating an individual pulse-shape profile for each particle. The particle-specific profiles reflect characteristics such as size, morphology, and pigment composition, which are then used to identify different particle populations (Dubelaar et al., 1999; Thyssen et al., 2022). A set of images taken from the sample can be used in the identification of the different particle populations for the CS instruments equipped with a camera.

Samples were acquired every hour from the same flow-through system as the other sensors at the Utö station. Sampling between 7 and 19 July 2021 did not occur due to a technical failure of CS. Three acquisition protocols were used to optimize information from the different size ranges in the community. The first protocol targeted picosized phytoplankton and was triggered on sideward scatter (30 mV) and analyzed a volume of $\sim 500\ \mu\text{l}$ at a flow rate of 2 $\mu\text{l/s}$. The other two protocols targeted nano and micro-sized phytoplankton and were triggered on the Chl *a* fluorescence (50 and 100 mV, for the nano and microphytoplankton, respectively) at a flow speed of 3.47 and 8.05 $\mu\text{l/s}$, yielding analyzed volumes of 500–1000 μl and 4.5–5 ml for nano and microphytoplankton, respectively. Clusters were identified manually using CytoClus4 (Cytobuoy, NL), and each particle was assigned to one cluster only. Filamentous cyanobacteria have distinctive optical fingerprints due to the PC content and ratio between particle length and total volume, however, the smaller sizes in the cluster can also contain other cyanobacteria with PC signal, as colonies can have similar signatures as short filaments. However, during the filamentous cyanobacteria bloom season (the study period; June–August) the cluster contains mainly long particles representing filamentous species, with little effect on the total biovolume/biomass from other taxa. The high-resolution camera of the instrument was not in use during this study, but high-resolution images from diverse phytoplankton cells ($n = 800$) obtained with the same instrument in previous campaigns were manually measured and converted to volumes using a geometrical approach (Sun and Liu, 2003). The obtained cell volumes were then compared with the integrated forward scatter of the particles to generate an empirical relationship to convert forward scatter to volume that was used in this study (see Haraguchi et al., 2017 for more details). Cell volumes were converted to biomass in the same way as with IFCB, according to CEN (2015).

2.5. Light microscopy analysis

A total of 20 samples for light microscopy analysis were taken approximately every other week in 2018, 2021, and 2022 from the station flow-through system. Samples (250 mL) were taken by filling the sample bottle from the flow-through line in the station building. The samples were preserved with acidic Lugol’s solution and kept refrigerated and in the dark until light microscopical analysis.

The light microscopy samples were analyzed according to Kraft et al.

(2021). In short, cyanobacterial abundance was estimated using the Utermöhl technique (Utermöhl, 1958). Depending on the sample density, 25 or 50 mL of the sample was settled in Utermöhl chambers, respectively, for 18 h or 24 h, and analyzed using an inverted light microscope. A magnification of 125x was used for *Aphanizomenon* spp., *Dolichospermum* spp., and *Nodularia* spp. Predefined size classes were used for counting (see Olenina et al., 2006) by choosing a suitable size class for each filament by visually estimating the filament widths with the help of an ocular micrometer. This counting method is used in HELCOM phytoplankton monitoring by the countries surrounding the Baltic Sea (HELCOM, 2023). The size classes and biovolumes used (Olenina et al., 2006) were subsequently converted to biomass ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), assuming a plasma density of 1 g cm^{-3} according to CEN (2015).

2.6. Frequency of Cyanobacteria Accumulations (FCA)

Satellite images show the spatial extent of cyanobacteria accumulations in high detail, but the coverage is typically patchy due to cloud cover. To normalize to the availability of clear views of the sea surface, the FCA method was developed (Kahru et al., 2007; Kahru and Elmgren, 2014). FCA is the ratio of the number of days when cyanobacteria accumulations were detected to the number of days with unobstructed (cloud-free) satellite views of the sea surface, calculated for each pixel. FCA is averaged over space (any number of pixels) and time (e.g., 5 days, 1 to 3 months). FCA is based on the detection of turbid water because of the increased reflectance of cyanobacteria surface accumulations in the red part of the visible spectrum. In the summer months, increased turbidity in the open Baltic Sea is mostly due to the accumulation of cyanobacteria, and thus FCA is highly correlated with the amount of cyanobacteria in the surface layer (Kahru and Elmgren, 2014).

To maximize temporal coverage, FCA was merged from 6 ocean colour sensors, each with $\sim 1 \text{ km}^2$ pixel size (MODIS-Aqua, MODIS-Terra, VIIRS-SNPP, VIIRS-JPSS1, OLCI-A, OLCI-B). The level-2 data were downloaded from the NASA Ocean Biology DAAC (<https://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/>). In near-shore and shallow areas, satellite ocean colour data do not represent turbidity accurately. Therefore, we could not calculate FCA data for the exact location of the Utö Station, which is adjacent to land. Instead, we calculated FCA in a circle with a diameter of 30 km centered at the Utö Station for 5-day intervals from June to the end of August. Different circle sizes were tested. A circle with a diameter of 30 km was found to be the best compromise to have nearly full temporal coverage at 5-day intervals and not too large spatial coverage. A total of 83 observations were included in this study. FCA ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 means that cyanobacteria were not detected and 1 means that cyanobacteria were detected for all pixels during the time interval in question (i.e., 5 days, in the present study). FCA can be presented as % by multiplying by 100.

2.7. Statistical analysis

Orthogonal regressions were performed and Pearson correlation coefficients calculated to determine if there was a statistical relationship between the different continuous measurements. IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria biomass was compared with CS, PC and Chl *a* fluorescence, and turbidity. IFCB total community was also compared with Chl *a* fluorescence and turbidity, and PC fluorescence, Chl *a* fluorescence and turbidity with each other. Additionally, PC fluorescence from the fluorometer was compared with PC fluorescence from the cluster containing the filamentous cyanobacteria from CS. Comparison was done for all data from June–August 2018, 2020, 2021, and 2022, except for turbidity (data missing from 2021) and CS (data only from 2021). Separate models were drawn for the yearly relationships and the multiyear data. Further taxon-specific (*Aphanizomenon*, *Dolichospermum*, *Nodularia*) relationships were tested between IFCB and light microscopy filamentous cyanobacteria biomass for 17 samples collected during 2018, 2021, and 2022. Both yearly and multiyear orthogonal regressions

were also performed for IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria biomass with a 5-day mean and FCA with corresponding time intervals.

All statistical tests used a significance level of <0.01 and were performed with R 3.6.1 (R Core Team, 2024). The tests used can be found in the basic R, except the function `odregress` that was used for computing the orthogonal regression, which is part of the `pracma` package (Borchers, 2023). The figures were produced with R using the `ggplot2` package (Wickham, 2016). The Pearson correlation coefficients were considered as very strong $r > 0.9$, strong $r = 0.7\text{--}0.9$, moderate $r = 0.5\text{--}0.7$, weak $r = 0.3\text{--}0.5$, and negligible $r = 0\text{--}0.3$.

3. Results

3.1. Overall development of the filamentous cyanobacteria season

The IFCB data showed that the filamentous cyanobacteria bloom season (biomass $> 200 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) started in late June or early July, depending on the year (Fig. 3). The biomass increased rapidly when the conditions became favorable for cyanobacteria growth and for their accumulation in a shallow mixed surface layer, at water temperatures of around $15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Fig. 3). In our study period, there was large variation in the total filamentous cyanobacteria maximum biomass between years, ranging from $550 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (in 2021) to around $2000 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (in 2020). The highest summer total phytoplankton community biomass (the whole community, including filamentous cyanobacteria) occurred when the water temperature reached close to $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Fig. 3). The most intensive bloom lasted approximately 1–2 weeks and was followed by secondary biomass peaks of a smaller magnitude (Fig. 3).

IFCB and FCA drew a consistent overall picture of the development of the summer cyanobacteria situation, although there was variation in the exact timing and length of the peak (Fig. 3). There was also a strong correlation between the methods ($r = 0.78, p < 0.001$, Fig. 4B, Table 2). Some of the fluctuations in FCA followed the total phytoplankton community biomass (Fig. 3).

Although the highest cyanobacteria biomass peaks were not captured by the light microscopy method when compared to IFCB, the timing of the light microscopy samples was (by pure chance) mainly off only by approximately a day. Nevertheless, the methods agreed on the coarse bloom development and the dominating species (Fig. 5). The greatest discrepancy in the observed maximum cyanobacteria biomasses was in 2018 when IFCB biomass reached $\sim 1400 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, but the highest recorded light microscopy biomass was only $\sim 850 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. There was a marked difference between the maximum biomasses determined by the methods also in 2021 and 2022 ($\sim 550 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ vs. $\sim 400 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $\sim 850 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ vs. $\sim 650 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively).

3.2. Taxon-specific community development with IFCB and microscopy

IFCB provides information on the total biomass of filamentous cyanobacteria, but even more importantly, on their taxon-specific dynamics. IFCB and light microscopy correlated strongly both at the taxon and total filamentous cyanobacteria levels (Fig. 4C). The taxon-specific relationships were stronger (r : *Aphanizomenon* = 0.87, *Dolichospermum* = 0.91, *Nodularia* = 0.99, $p < 0.001$) than for the total filamentous cyanobacteria ($r = 0.85, p < 0.001$, Fig. 4C, Table 2). Despite the linear relationship, it was not one-to-one: IFCB consistently estimated biomass as half of the light microscopy biomass for *Nodularia* and *Aphanizomenon*. Conversely, for *Dolichospermum*, IFCB biomass estimates were approximately twice the light microscopy biomasses (Fig. 4C). The linear relationships of the total filamentous cyanobacteria biomasses were closer to one-to-one, with light microscopy tending to produce somewhat higher biomasses (Fig. 4C).

IFCB and light microscopy agreed on the biomass level (high or low). However, the magnitude varied, with different methods alternately estimating higher and lower biomass, still largely agreeing on the dominant taxa (Fig. 5). The interannual differences in the magnitude of

Fig. 3. Time series of hourly IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria (dark grey) and total phytoplankton (grey) biomass, Chl *a* fluorescence (green), PC fluorescence (blue), turbidity (purple), and water temperature (dark red) during the summer cyanobacteria season for different years in Utö. The IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria observations are also shown as a 5-day average (gold) with a corresponding interval to FCA (dark gold). Note that the y-axis is for turbidity, PC and Chl *a* fluorescence, and biomass; the secondary y-axis is for temperature and FCA. The parameters and y-axis values are separated by the corresponding /.

the total filamentous cyanobacteria biomass (Fig. 5) reflected the taxon-specific differences between IFCB and light microscopy (Fig. 4C) (i.e., the light microscopy biomass of total filamentous cyanobacteria was higher than with IFCB in times when *Aphanizomenon* or *Nodularia* were dominating and vice versa when *Dolichospermum* was dominating). In the year 2018, *Aphanizomenon* and *Dolichospermum* were the main contributors to the high filamentous cyanobacteria biomass with approximately equal shares (Fig. 5A). In 2020, the total biomass was even higher ($\sim 2000 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), but it consisted almost exclusively of *Aphanizomenon* (Fig. 5B). In 2021 and 2022, the cyanobacteria bloom was modest, with *Dolichospermum* starting the bloom in late June and collapsing shortly after that (Fig. 5C, D). While in 2021, *Dolichospermum* declined concurrently with a fast increase in only *Aphanizomenon* biomass (Fig. 5C), in 2022, *Dolichospermum* declined simultaneously with the increase of both *Aphanizomenon* and *Nodularia*, although none of them developed high biomass levels, such as the highest biomass peaks in 2018 and 2020 (Fig. 5D).

3.3. Comparison of high-throughput cyanobacteria observations

PC fluorescence followed IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria biomass closely both when cyanobacteria occurred in low and high biomass (Fig. 3). They also had a strong relationship ($r = 0.86$, $p < 0.001$, Fig. 4D, Table 2.), especially in years of high cyanobacteria biomass (2018, 2020, $r > 0.9$, $p < 0.001$, Supplementary Table 1). During the years 2018 and 2020, when filamentous cyanobacteria were most abundant, both Chl *a* and PC fluorescence peaked approximately together with the IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria biomass (Fig. 3A, B). However, in 2018, the peak of Chl *a* fluorescence was more scattered, extending to the decline phase of the cyanobacteria bloom, when other than filamentous cyanobacteria had a greater share of the total community. During the low filamentous cyanobacteria biomass year 2021, the Chl *a* fluorescence peak occurred only clearly after the IFCB cyanobacteria biomass peak, when phytoplankton other than cyanobacteria peaked (Fig. 3C). Still, in 2022 with rather low filamentous cyanobacteria biomass both PC and Chl *a* fluorescence peaked also approximately at the same time with

Fig. 4. Multiyear or taxon-specific orthogonal regressions of the parameters, except for panels with CS (A, G), for which there was data for 2021 only. The equation is from the orthogonal regression with Pearson correlation coefficient, and the grey line is the regression line; the dashed line is a 1:1 line in panels A and C. The colors indicate a year, taxon, or date of the period, as shown in the panel legend.

Table 2

Orthogonal regressions and Pearson correlation coefficients for the multi-year and taxon-specific data organized based on the Pearson r .

	intercept	slope	r	p -value	n
IFCB - Light microscopy, <i>Nodularia</i>	-0.7	1.84	0.99	<0.001	17
IFCB - CS, Filam cyanobacteria	-20.66	1.2	0.93	<0.001	1637
IFCB - Light microscopy, <i>Dolichospermum</i>	2.35	0.7	0.91	<0.001	17
IFCB - Light microscopy, <i>Aphanizomenon</i>	-28.65	2.29	0.87	<0.001	17
IFCB filam cyanobacteria - PC fluorescence	1.23	0.0086	0.86	<0.001	6022
IFCB - Light microscopy, Filam cyanobacteria	-35.25	1.84	0.85	<0.001	17
Fluorometer - CS, PC fluorescence	-28,559,598	19,567,628	0.80	<0.001	1803
IFCB filam cyanobacteria - Turbidity	0.26	0.00044	0.79	<0.001	4676
IFCB filam cyanobacteria - FCA	0.014	0.00032	0.78	<0.001	57
IFCB total community - Chl a fluorescence	1.2	0.0016	0.73	<0.001	6635
IFCB total community - Turbidity	0.21	0.00018	0.72	<0.001	4676
Chl a fluorescence - Turbidity	0.12	0.093	0.70	<0.001	5386
PC fluorescence - Turbidity	0.23	0.041	0.69	<0.001	4665
Chl a fluorescence - PC fluorescence	-4.45	2.93	0.41	<0.001	6840
IFCB filam cyanobacteria - Chl a fluorescence	1.96	0.0024	0.40	<0.001	6635

IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria biomass (Fig. 3D). Turbidity followed the same trends as PC fluorescence and IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria biomass, although other smaller peaks in turbidity occurred simultaneously with Chl a fluorescence and total phytoplankton community biomass peaks (Fig. 3). IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria biomass had only a weak linear relationship with Chl a fluorescence ($r = 0.4$, $p < 0.001$, Fig. 4F, Table 2), but strong with turbidity ($r = 0.79$, $p < 0.001$, Fig. 4E, Table 2).

The multiyear total phytoplankton community biomass measured using the IFCB correlated with Chl a fluorescence ($r = 0.73$, $p < 0.001$) even though the total community biomass is a crude summing up of all images in a sample without any type of classification or filtering out of possible non-living particles (the assumption being that when using Chl a as a trigger, most images should be of living particles) (Fig. 4I, Table 2). Looking at the years separately, IFCB total phytoplankton community biomass had a stronger relationship with Chl a fluorescence in the year with a modest filamentous cyanobacteria bloom (2021 $r = 0.92$, $p < 0.001$, Supplementary Table 1). An exception in the IFCB total phytoplankton community biomass and Chl a relationship was the year 2022, when the relationship was very weak ($r = 0.36$, $p < 0.001$, Supplementary Table 1). The multiyear IFCB total phytoplankton community biomass had a linear relationship also with turbidity ($r = 0.72$, $p < 0.001$, Fig. 4H, Table 2).

There were linear relationships, albeit not very strong ones, between Chl a fluorescence and turbidity ($r = 0.7$, $p < 0.001$, Fig. 4K, Table 2) and PC fluorescence and turbidity ($r = 0.69$, $p < 0.001$, Fig. 4J, Table 2), but the relationship between Chl a and PC fluorescence was weak ($r = 0.41$, $p < 0.001$, Fig. 4L, Table 2). The CS PC fluorescence correlated strongly with the fluorometer PC fluorescence ($r = 0.8$, $p < 0.001$), and the observations followed a pattern related to the progress of the filamentous cyanobacteria bloom (Fig. 4G). IFCB and CS corresponded on the development of the cyanobacteria biomass during both bloom and lower

biomass situations in 2021 with very strong (almost 1:1) linear relationship ($r = 0.93$, $p < 0.001$, Fig. 5C, Fig. 4A, Table 2). However, during the bloom peak, when biomass was $> 500 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, CS total biomass was markedly higher than IFCB (Fig. 5C, Fig. 4A).

4. Discussion

4.1. IFCB and light microscopy

Cyanobacteria enumeration with imaging flow cytometry has previously been compared to light microscopy counts with a good agreement between the methods (Graham et al., 2018; Hrycik et al., 2019; Kraft et al., 2021). The instruments used in the previous studies were the benchtop instrument FlowCam (Fluid Imaging Technologies, U.S., Sieracki et al., 1998) by Graham et al. (2018) and Hrycik et al. (2019), and the in situ instrument IFCB by Kraft et al. (2021). In the present study, IFCB and light microscopy filamentous cyanobacteria biomass had a linear relationship, similar to that in Hrycik et al. (2019) between FlowCam and light microscopy. The two methods described the blooms similarly, but they differed in exact biomass values (Figs. 4C, 5), thus confirming the findings of Kraft et al. (2021; their data from 2018 are included in the present study). We found light microscopy counts to be higher than IFCB counts for *Aphanizomenon* (as did Graham et al., 2018 with FlowCam and light microscopy) and for *Nodularia*, approximately twofold for both taxa. Graham et al. (2018) had a relationship following almost exactly the 1:1 line for *Anabaena* sp., whereas our IFCB counts were twofold compared with light microscopy for the morphologically corresponding *Dolichospermum*. The potential reasons for these deviations were discussed in Kraft et al. (2021) and include large filament coils and bundles not being captured by the imaging flow cytometer, and the biovolumes of large filament bundles being underestimated by the biovolume calculations from the images (Graham et al., 2018). Also, the use of size classes in light microscopy counting (100 μm piece of filament) may result in an inaccurate estimation of the size class, which is chosen based on filament width and cell shape (spherical or cylindrical).

4.2. High-throughput phytoplankton instruments IFCB and CS

Both IFCB and CS can be used to characterize phytoplankton community composition with high frequency, but their imaging and cytometric properties differ. The primary data of IFCB are the images (Olson and Sosik, 2007), while the primary data of CS are the pulse shape profiles, and the images are taken as a subset in a sample to help with the identification of different clusters of these pulse shape profiles (Dubelaar et al., 1999). To our knowledge, previous studies comparing the two instruments do not exist. Our results show that the overall filamentous cyanobacteria bloom patterns were consistent between the IFCB and CS (Fig. 5C). Based on the one-year data, the linear relationship between the two instruments for filamentous cyanobacteria biomass was very strong (Fig. 4A). The only deviation between the instruments was at high biomass values of over $500 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, with CS estimating higher biomasses than IFCB.

Several factors may affect the differences in IFCB and CS results for the high biomass values, some being the same as those between IFCB and light microscopy. One important issue is that the size range of the particles that can be analyzed by the IFCB is 10–150 μm because of the camera resolution and a 150 μm prefilter at the inlet, whereas the size range of CS is 0.2–800 μm (Lombard et al., 2019). Filaments as long as 300 μm do get sampled by IFCB (Kraft et al., 2021; Dugenne et al., 2023), but the prefiltering likely rejects large filament bundles, coils, and aggregates, which could explain some of the difference, but it should not have a major impact as the median filament biovolumes between the methods were close to each other at the time of the biggest difference (Supplementary figure 2). Using the correction factors for coiled *Dolichospermum* (Kraft et al., 2021) and coiled *Nodularia* in IFCB samples may also cause some difference between IFCB and CS results, since the

Fig. 5. The taxon-specific and total filamentous cyanobacteria biomass from IFCB (small colored symbols), and light microscopy (big empty black symbols) in yearly panels. The total filamentous cyanobacteria biomass of CS is in the background with grey only in 2021 (panel C). The y-axis is square root transformed to make it easier to distinguish low biomass fluctuations.

corresponding correction has not been implemented for the CS. This could explain some of the high biomass values being estimated as higher with CS than with IFCB. A likely overall explanation could be that CS can record bigger coils, which more often have overestimated biovolumes. The number of those bigger coils is likely higher during the bloom peak because the overall number of filaments is higher, which leads to the accumulation of the bigger biovolumes during the bloom peak.

4.3. IFCB, CS, and bulk bio-optical instruments

The bulk phytoplankton community has been monitored by fluorescence measurements using Chl *a* for decades (Lorenzen, 1966), and Chl *a* in situ fluorescence has been used in the Finnish marine

monitoring since the early 1990s (Rantajarvi et al., 2020). For cyanobacteria specifically, Chl *a* is not the best proxy because cyanobacteria have a special pigment composition, and the fluorescing properties of cyanobacteria Chl *a* are low (Seppälä et al., 2005; Watanabe and Ikeuchi, 2013). The relationship between Chl *a* and cyanobacteria differs whether in vivo fluorescence or extracted concentration is used. Most of the Chl *a* in cyanobacteria is located in the non-fluorescing photosystem I, which is why it does not contribute to the in vivo Chl *a* fluorescence, and therefore the filtered Chl *a* concentration describes its abundance better (Seppälä et al., 2007; Rome et al., 2021). Nevertheless, due to the common use of Chl *a* as a phytoplankton proxy, the European Water Framework Directive and the World Health Organization suggest using Chl *a* concentration with cell counts as an alert of harmful

concentrations of cyanobacteria (Almuhtaram et al., 2021).

The relationship between IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria biomass and Chl *a* fluorescence was weak, as expected, and Chl *a* fluorescence was better related to the IFCB total phytoplankton community biomass (Fig. 4F, D). The multiyear correlation between IFCB total phytoplankton community and Chl *a* fluorescence was strong, but there was large variation between years (Supplementary table 1). A likely explanation for the variation in the yearly relationships is the overall community composition, but to confirm that, a closer examination of the phytoplankton community is needed.

PC fluorescence (also PE fluorescence) is more specific for cyanobacteria than Chl *a*, and therefore a better proxy for cyanobacteria (Seppälä et al., 2005, 2007). PC fluorescence and IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria biomass followed the same trends very closely throughout the study period, and at both high and low cyanobacteria biomass (Fig. 3). PC fluorescence and cyanobacteria total biovolume and cell concentrations have been shown to have a linear relationship in freshwater environments (Brient et al., 2008; McQuaid et al., 2011; Thomson-Laing et al., 2020) and experiments with cultures (Bastien et al., 2011). In the Baltic Sea, Seppälä et al. (2007) and Karlson et al. (2022) compared PC fluorescence to light microscopy counts of filamentous cyanobacteria along a FerryBox line (an autonomous measurement system onboard a commercial vessel). In both studies, there was a linear relationship between the cyanobacteria biomass and PC fluorescence, as in this study (Fig. 4D). It could be tested in the future by combining the results of this study with the results by Seppälä et al. (2007) and by Karlson et al. (2022), as the PC fluorescence sensors used in all studies are calibrated using the same methods and thus should produce comparable readings. That way, it could be concluded how universal the relationship between PC fluorescence and filamentous cyanobacteria biomass is in the Baltic Sea. It would also indicate whether the two different methods for the biomass (IFCB and light microscopy) affect the relationship and whether there are differences depending on, e.g., the growth phase of the bloom.

As a proxy for cyanobacteria, turbidity has previously been found to correlate with PC fluorescence (Yang et al., 2019) and with cell counts (Rome et al., 2021). Turbidity, or light scattering in general, is related to the amount of phytoplankton, suspended sediments, and other particles. In phytoplankton, turbidity is affected by internal cell structures, and gas vacuoles inside cyanobacteria could increase their scattering properties (Matthews and Bernard, 2013). In this study, especially the yearly cyanobacteria biomasses correlated well with turbidity, but the multi-year correlation was slightly weaker. This might indicate that the relationship is not so well generalized, with the yearly differences being greater. Seppälä et al. (2007) showed that turbidity measurements contained more noise than fluorescence measurements and therefore turbidity is not as stable and clear a proxy. In this study, turbidity followed the same trends as PC fluorescence and IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria biomass, but other smaller peaks in turbidity occurred simultaneously with Chl *a* fluorescence, and there was a linear relationship also between turbidity and the IFCB total phytoplankton community, demonstrating how turbidity can be affected by other phytoplankton groups. However, during a known filamentous cyanobacteria bloom, turbidity can be used to describe the bloom development since the majority of seston at that time consists of cyanobacteria. Often, it is not feasible to have expensive high-frequency imaging instruments like IFCB deployed in multiple locations. If PC fluorescence instruments are not available, turbidity sensors can provide a low-cost alternative for following cyanobacteria bloom development at a high temporal frequency, but only as a supplement to identification methods such as light microscopy samples.

The observations of the bulk properties (pigments and scattering signals) are affected by the species composition and can also be affected by the overall state of the cells in the water column, which is determined by the individual cell physiology (Ziegmann et al., 2010). CS can record the optical characteristics of the individual particles, reflecting the cell

morphology and physiology (Dubelaar et al., 1999; Haraguchi et al., 2017). In 2021, the filamentous cyanobacteria biomass estimated by CS and IFCB was in close agreement, while differences were observed between the total PC fluorescence from the fluorometer and CS. This can partially be explained by the fact that PC in CS is excited by the 594 nm laser and detected over a 604–644 nm band, which differs from the settings of the fluorometer (ex./em. 640/655 nm). The contributions of the phycobilins (PEC, PC, APC) affect the measurement differently when using these wavelengths, and a possible reason for the differing results may be that the pigmentation of cyanobacteria changes during the bloom, either due to changes in species composition or cell physiology. Another possibility for the difference could be that during the late stages of the bloom, some phycobilins may become decoupled from other pigments, and their fluorescence properties are changed (Moldaenke et al., 2019). The relationship of CS with PC fluorescence (Fig. 4G) seems to follow a temporal pattern with higher CS-PC yields in late June compared to late July. Such shifts correspond to different bloom compositions recorded with IFCB, in late June corresponding to the dominance of *Dolichospermum*, and in late July to a mix of *Dolichospermum* and *Aphanizomenon*. The shifts in the relationship of CS-PC with PC fluorescence could further be affected by cell physiology. Investigation of the topic could help elucidate some of the competition mechanisms among different taxa, but this will remain a topic for future studies.

4.4. Overall cyanobacteria bloom succession as observed with IFCB and FCA

The Baltic Sea cyanobacteria blooms start to develop in June, with surface accumulations forming usually in July–August, depending on the area (Kahru and Elmgren, 2014). The overall bloom density varies and is mainly related to favorable environmental conditions, such as water temperature, wind, and phosphorus availability in the surface water (Sellner, 1997; Wasmund et al., 1997; Lips and Lips, 2008). In the present study, the IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria biomass started to increase exponentially in mid-June or early July, with the main biomass peak lasting approximately 1–2 weeks. The biomass increased rapidly when the water temperature rose to around 15 °C, which is in line with previous investigations (e.g. Wasmund et al., 1997; Kanoshina et al., 2003). Wasmund et al. (1997) suggested that a cyanobacteria biomass higher than 200 µg L⁻¹ would be defined as a bloom. Thus, even in the year with the lowest maximum biomass (2021, 550 µg L⁻¹), the cyanobacteria can be considered to have formed blooms in the study area. The cyanobacteria community composition differed between years, the two mainly dominating taxa being *Aphanizomenon* and *Dolichospermum*, while *Nodularia* was abundant only in 2022 (Fig. 4). The variation in taxon-related dynamics was great over the years. The bloom was either dominated by only one taxon or co-dominated by two or all three taxa, with varying taxon-specific biomasses.

In the long term, when the yearly surface accumulations are averaged over larger areas, they usually occur after mid-July in the Northern Baltic Proper (Kahru and Elmgren, 2014). However, there are indications of an earlier onset of the summer bloom season during the past decades based on FCA observations (Kahru et al., 2016). The timing of the yearly highest IFCB bloom peak in our study, taking place from late June to mid-July, supports the shift in the timing of the blooms from after mid-July to earlier in the summer. The IFCB filamentous cyanobacteria biomass peaks coincided with the peaks in the satellite-derived FCA in this study, demonstrating that the earlier timing is not related to the two methods detecting different bloom stages. The timing of the bloom peak could also be affected by the environmental conditions of the study site becoming favorable earlier than in the open pelagic, however, the timing of the peak in filamentous cyanobacteria biomass off Utö as detected by IFCB coincides well with the seasonal cycle detected by FCA for the whole Northern Baltic Proper.

The cyanobacteria blooms in the Baltic Sea are spatially very heterogeneous (Almesjö, 2007; Seppälä et al., 2007). We calculated FCA for

an area centered 30 km from the Utö station, still, the blooms were described similarly by FCA and IFCB. The bloom fluctuations, however, did not coincide exactly, which is understandable due to the patchiness of the blooms and the different nature of the observations. The cyanobacteria biomass probably also starts to build up before the formation of the surface accumulations, therefore, the biomass accumulation detected by IFCB (with the sample water coming from ~5 m depth) may occur slightly earlier than indicated by the FCA. There was a linear relationship between FCA and IFCB (Fig. 4B), as in Kahru and Elmgren (2014) between FCA and PC fluorescence. On the contrary, Karlson et al. (2022) did not find any relationship between FCA and filamentous cyanobacteria biomass derived from light microscopy samples. The different results between these studies may reflect the light microscopy samples being too infrequent to agree with FCA, as suggested by Karlson et al. (2022). The cyanobacteria data in this study and the study by Kahru and Elmgren (2014) were from high-frequency sensors. Furthermore, the samples in the study by Karlson et al. (2022) were integrated samples from 0 to 10 (some 0–20)-meter depth, i.e., representing a thicker water layer than in the present study, which may further have contributed to no relationship being found between the methods.

4.5. Perspectives on bloom monitoring

The frequency of the phytoplankton observations does matter, as demonstrated recently by Sonnet et al. (2024) using IFCB data. They concluded that even with a weekly sampling interval, the smaller biomass peaks are often missed, and larger blooms are either underestimated or overestimated. Both effects are also visible in our data when looking at the hourly IFCB cyanobacteria biomass and the approximately every other week collected light microscopy data. When comparing the IFCB cyanobacteria biomass results to long-term time series with traditional monitoring frequency, it is apparent that with the high-frequency method, the highest biomass maximum can be described more precisely, in addition to the overall bloom phenology. Altogether, for a period from 1979 to 2016, Olofsson et al. (2020) reported from the Northern Baltic Proper the highest total cyanobacteria biomass as around 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, which is only half of the highest biomass recorded in our study during an *Aphanizomenon*-dominated bloom in 2020, although the studies are not directly comparable because the periods do not overlap.

The sampling stations in the study by Olofsson et al. (2020) representing the Northern Baltic Proper are monitoring stations, of which two are visited only 1–2 times per summer, and two are stations that may be visited more frequently. The Finnish open sea phytoplankton monitoring stations are sampled only once per summer, in August. Assuming that the Utö cyanobacterial situation is representative of the situation in the Finnish open sea areas in general, the timing of the August sampling is not ideal for catching the cyanobacterial bloom peak, or at least no longer is; this is also supported by the findings by Kahru et al. (2016).

Imaging flow cytometry has not yet been extensively adopted for monitoring by the countries in the European Union, although being identified as a potential method (Korpinen et al., 2022). Almuhtaram et al. (2021) reviewed the available tools for cyanobacteria monitoring, proposing a three-tier framework, where tools were grouped by their analytical targets, to assist in the design of early warning systems. Their assessment, however, did not cover in situ imaging flow cytometry, probably because the publications for targeting cyanobacteria have been mainly published only after their review (Kraft et al., 2021; Doppler et al., 2022). de Figueiredo (2024) also reviewed the available methods and proposed a scheme from bloom detection to an integrated database, but that scheme lacked imaging flow cytometry: while it was included in the review itself, the scheme was only based on more common methods. We have further collected the advantages and limitations of the methods or instruments used in this study to help assess potential methods to meet different needs (Table 3).

The above recent reviews demonstrate that while in situ imaging

Table 3

The advantages and limitations of the methods/ instruments used identified in this study.

Method/ Instrument	Advantages	Limitations
IFCB	high temporal resolution, taxonomic information, possibility for real time information	requires user knowledge, high investment cost, taxonomic identification in some cases limited
CS	high temporal resolution, taxonomic information, possibility for real time information	requires user knowledge, high investment cost, taxonomic identification in some cases limited
Light microscopy	detailed taxonomic information, long term time-series exist	requires high expertise, time-consuming analysis, low temporal resolution
PC fluorescence	easy, low cost, very high temporal resolution	calibration can be challenging, lack of taxonomic information
Chl <i>a</i> fluorescence	easy, low cost, very high temporal resolution	calibration can be challenging, lack of taxonomic information
Turbidity	easy, low cost, very high temporal resolution	calibration can be challenging, lack of taxonomic information
FCA	wide spatial coverage, representative on medium to wide spatial scales, no cost	clouds hinder data collection, lack of taxonomic information

flow cytometry is an emerging method with a recognized potential for phytoplankton studies (e.g., Lombard et al., 2019), and the method has been adopted for early warning systems in marine environments (e.g., Ruiz-Villarreal et al., 2022), its potential has not yet been put to use in the monitoring of cyanobacteria. This may be due to the lack of publications demonstrating its applicability specifically for the colony-forming cyanobacterium *Microcystis*, which is a very common bloom-forming and potentially toxin-producing genus in freshwater environments. Since most studies on bloom-forming cyanobacteria are from freshwater environments, whereas most imaging flow cytometry studies are from the marine environment, studies combining both are scarce. The reasons why in situ imaging flow cytometry is not yet being widely implemented in cyanobacteria monitoring may also relate to the somewhat high investment cost of the method.

The in situ imaging flow cytometer publications (van Dijk et al., 2010; Doppler et al., 2022 on CS, and Kraft et al., 2021; Dugenne et al., 2023 on IFCB) have targeted filamentous taxa, but other cyanobacteria can also be identified from the images, including colonial forms (Kraft et al., 2022). The possible level of identification depends on the target taxon and the surrounding community, meaning that if other similar taxa are present, the target taxon can be more easily confused with them. Differentiation to the species level is often impossible with in situ imaging flow cytometry because species-level identification often requires detailed scrutiny of the sample, e.g., in the case of Baltic Sea bloom-forming filamentous taxa, this would mean the observation of the shape of vegetative cells, and the relative size as well as shape and location of heterocytes and akinetes (Komárek, 2013). However, the differentiation to the species level is in many cases also challenging with light microscopy. It requires high taxonomical expertise to identify many of the species. With imaging flow cytometry, the different taxa can often be separated to genus level, which is usually sufficient for cyanobacteria bloom monitoring (e.g., Kraft et al., 2022).

5. Conclusions

Overall, the different methods investigated in this study described

the observed filamentous cyanobacteria bloom development similarly, although there were also some differences. IFCB and light microscopy agreed on the dominating taxa, but the exact biomass values deviated, and the methods estimated the biomass of the taxa differently (for *Dolichospermum* IFCB estimates were twofold, and for *Aphanizomenon* and *Nodularia* light microscopy estimates were twofold). When data from bio-optical sensors were compared to cyanobacteria biomass estimated by the IFCB, filamentous cyanobacteria biomass had the strongest relationship with PC fluorescence, followed by turbidity, and had no relationship with Chl *a* fluorescence. Albeit being slightly different (from the operational point of view) high-throughput instruments for phytoplankton community characterization, IFCB and CS produced comparable results of the filamentous cyanobacteria bloom. When IFCB biomass results were compared to FCA, the cyanobacteria bloom season was characterized similarly by the two methods, despite FCA having a different spatial coverage. We conclude that high-throughput imaging flow cytometry is comparable to and combinable with the other tested methods used for cyanobacteria monitoring. High-throughput imaging flow cytometry provides valuable information on high-frequency taxon-specific community dynamics that cannot be obtained using bulk measurements or the low sampling frequency connected with the traditional methods, and there is enormous potential for its use in cyanobacteria monitoring. The best overall understanding of the cyanobacteria blooms is attained with a combination of different methods covering wide temporal and spatial scales.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kaisa Kraft: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lumi Haraguchi:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Heidi Hällfors:** Writing – review & editing. **Sanna Suikkanen:** Writing – review & editing. **Pasi Ylöstalo:** Investigation. **Sami Kielosto:** Investigation. **Annaliina Skyttä:** Software, Investigation. **Lauri Laakso:** Writing – review & editing. **Martti Honkanen:** Software, Investigation, Data curation. **Mati Kahru:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Jukka Seppälä:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors are thankful to the two anonymous reviewers for their constructive reviews and valuable comments that helped improve this manuscript. This study utilized research infrastructure as part of FIN-MARI (Finnish Marine Research Infrastructure consortium). KK, AS, SS, and HH were supported by the Academy of Finland project FASTVISION-plus (Grant no 339355). JS, PY, LL, and MH were supported by JERICO-S3 (Grant Agreement No 871153) funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe program. LH was supported by OBAMA-NEXT (Grant Agreement No 101081642), funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe program. The authors wish to acknowledge CSC – IT Center for Science, Finland, for computational resources. The authors want to thank Simo-Matti Siirä and Katri Kuuppo for allowing the use of their images/ illustrations in Fig. 1.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.hal.2025.102865](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2025.102865).

Data availability

The dataset is publicly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15357836>.

References

- Almesjö, L., 2007. Filamentous cyanobacteria in the Baltic Sea - spatiotemporal patterns and nitrogen fixation. University.
- Almuharam, H., Kibuye, F.A., Ajampur, S., Glover, C.M., Hofmann, R., Gaget, V., et al., 2021. State of knowledge on early warning tools for cyanobacteria detection. *Ecol. Indic.* 133, 108442. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.108442>.
- Bastien, C., Cardin, R., Veilleux, É., Deblois, C., Warren, A., Laurion, L., 2011. Performance evaluation of phycocyanin probes for the monitoring of cyanobacteria. *J. Env. Monit.* 13, 110–118. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C0EM00366B>.
- Bertani, I., Steger, C.E., Obenour, D.R., Fahnenstiel, G.L., Bridgeman, T.B., Johengen, T. H., et al., 2017. Tracking cyanobacteria blooms: do different monitoring approaches tell the same story? *Sci. Tot. Env.* 575, 294–308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.10.023>.
- Bertone, E., Burford, M.A., Hamilton, D.P., 2018. Fluorescence probes for real-time remote cyanobacteria monitoring: a review of challenges and opportunities. *Water. Res.* 141, 152–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2018.05.001>.
- Borchers, H. (2023). Practical numerical math routines. <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/pracma/pracma.pdf>. doi:10.32614/CRAN.package.pracma.
- Brient, L., Lengronne, M., Bertrand, E., Rolland, D., Sipel, A., Steinmann, D., et al., 2008. A phycocyanin probe as a tool for monitoring cyanobacteria in freshwater bodies. *J. Env. Monit.* 10, 248–255. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B714238B>.
- CEN 2015: DIN EN 16695 water quality – guidance on the estimation of phytoplankton biovolume: english version EN 16695:2015.
- de Figueiredo, D.R., 2024. Harmful cyanobacterial blooms: going beyond the “green” to monitor and predict HCBs. *Hydrobiology* 3 (1), 11–30. <https://doi.org/10.3390/hydrobiology3010002>.
- Doppler, P., Kriechbaum, R., Spadiut, O., 2022. High-throughput characterization of the filamentous cyanobacterium *anabaena* sp. using flow cytometry. *J. Microbiol. Methods* 199, 106510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mimet.2022.106510>.
- Dubelaar, G.B., Gerritzen, P.L., Beeker, A.E., Jonker, R.R., Tangen, K., 1999. Design and first results of CytoBuoy: a wireless flow cytometer for in situ analysis of marine and fresh waters. *Cytom.: J. Int. Soc. Anal. Cyt.* 37, 247–254. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0320\(19991201\)37:4<247::AID-CYTO1>3.0.CO;2-9](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0320(19991201)37:4<247::AID-CYTO1>3.0.CO;2-9).
- Dugene, M., Gradoville, M.R., Church, M.J., Wilson, S.T., Sheyn, U., Harke, M.J., Zehr, J.P., 2023. Nitrogen fixation in mesoscale eddies of the North Pacific subtropical gyre: patterns and mechanisms. *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycles* 37, e2022GB007386. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GB007386>.
- Graham, M.D., Cook, J., Graydon, J., Kinniburgh, D., Nelson, H., Pilić, S., et al., 2018. High-resolution imaging particle analysis of freshwater cyanobacterial blooms. *Limnol. Ocean. Methods* 16, 669–679. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lom3.10274>.
- Haraguchi, L., Jakobsen, H., Lundholm, N., Carstensen, J., 2017. Monitoring natural phytoplankton communities: a comparison between traditional methods and pulse-shape recording flow cytometry. *Aquat. Microb. Ecol.* 80, 77–92. <https://doi.org/10.3354/ame01842>.
- HELCOM, 2016. Guidelines for Monitoring of Chlorophyll *a*. HELCOM, Helsinki, Finland, p. 5. <https://doi.org/10.25607/OBP-1064> pp.
- HELCOM, 2023. Guidelines for monitoring of phytoplankton species composition, abundance and biomass. In *Manual for Marine Monitoring in the COMBINE Programme of HELCOM*. <https://helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/Guide-lines-for-monitoring-of-phytoplankton-species-composition-abundance-and-biomass-1.pdf> [Accessed March 22, 2024].
- Honkanen, M., Aurela, M., Hatakka, J., Haraguchi, L., Kielosto, S., Mäkelä, T., et al., 2024. Interannual and seasonal variability of the air-sea CO₂ exchange at Utö in the coastal region of the Baltic Sea. *Biogeosciences* 21, 4341–4359. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-21-4341-2024>.
- Honkanen, M., Müller, J.D., Seppälä, J., Rehder, G., Kielosto, S., Ylöstalo, P., et al., 2021. The diurnal cycle of pCO₂ in the coastal region of the Baltic Sea. *Ocean Sci.* 17, 1657–1675. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-17-1657-2021>.
- Hryciak, A.R., Shambaugh, A., Stockwell, J.D., 2019. Comparison of FlowCAM and microscope biovolume measurements for a diverse freshwater phytoplankton community. *J. Plankton Res.* 41, 849–864. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbz056>.
- Huisman, J., Codd, G.A., Paerl, H.W., Ibelings, B.W., Verspagen, J.M., Visser, P.M., 2018. Cyanobacterial blooms. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* 16, 471–483. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-018-0040-1>.
- Kahru, M., Elmgren, R., 2014. Multidecadal time series of satellite-detected accumulations of cyanobacteria in the Baltic Sea. *Biogeosciences* 11, 3619–3633. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-11-3619-2014>.
- Kahru, M., Elmgren, R., Savchuk, O.P., 2016. Changing seasonality of the Baltic Sea. *Biogeosciences* 13, 1009–1018. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-13-1009-2016>.
- Kahru, M., Savchuk, O.P., Elmgren, R., 2007. Satellite measurements of cyanobacterial bloom frequency in the Baltic Sea: interannual and spatial variability. *Mar. Ecol. Progr. Ser.* 343, 15–23. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps06943>.
- Kanoshina, I., Lips, U., Leppänen, J.M., 2003. The influence of weather conditions (temperature and wind) on cyanobacterial bloom development in the Gulf of Finland (Baltic Sea). *Harmful. Algae* 2, 29–41. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1568-9883\(02\)00085-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1568-9883(02)00085-9).
- Karlson, B., Arneborg, L., Johansson, J., Linders, J., Liu, Y., Olofsson, M., 2022. A suggested climate service for cyanobacteria blooms in the Baltic Sea—comparing

- three monitoring methods. *Harmful. Algae* 118, 102291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2022.102291>.
- Komárek, J., 2013. Cyanoprokaryota. 3. Teil /3rd part: Heterocystous Genera. – Süßwasserflora von Mitteleuropa (Freshwater Flora of Central Europe). Springer Spektrum Berlin, Heidelberg, p. 1130.
- Korpinen, S., Kahlert, M., Kuosa, H., Mack, L., Meissner, K., Pitkänen, H., et al., 2022. Marine monitoring in transition: on the verge of technological revolution? *Front. Mar. Sci.* 9, 1066769. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.1066769>.
- Kraft, K., Seppälä, J., Hällfors, H., Suikkanen, S., Ylöstalo, P., Anglès, S., et al., 2021. First application of IFCB high-frequency imaging-in-flow cytometry to investigate bloom-forming filamentous cyanobacteria in the Baltic Sea. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 8, 282. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.594144>.
- Kraft, K., Velhonoja, O., Eerola, T., Suikkanen, S., Tamminen, T., Haraguchi, L., et al., 2022. Towards operational phytoplankton recognition with automated high-throughput imaging, near-real-time data processing, and convolutional neural networks. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 9, 867695. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.867695>.
- Kramer, S.J., Bolaños, L.M., Catlett, D., Chase, A.P., Behrenfeld, M.J., Boss, E.S., et al., 2024. Toward a synthesis of phytoplankton communities composition methods for global-scale application. *Limnol. Ocean. Methods.* <https://doi.org/10.1002/lom3.10602>.
- Kramer, S.J., Siegel, D.A., Maritorea, S., Catlett, D., 2022. Modeling surface ocean phytoplankton pigments from hyperspectral remote sensing reflectance on global scales. *Remote Sens. Env.* 270, 112879. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2021.112879>.
- Laakso, L., Mikkonen, S., Drebs, A., Karjalainen, A., Pirinen, P., Alenius, P., 2018. 100 years of atmospheric and marine observations at the Finnish Utö Island in the Baltic Sea. *Ocean Sci.* 14, 617–632. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-14-617-2018>.
- Lips, I., Lips, U., 2008. Abiotic factors influencing cyanobacterial bloom development in the Gulf of Finland (Baltic Sea). *Hydrobiologia* 614, 133–140. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-008-9449-2>.
- Lombard, F., Boss, E., Waite, A.M., Uitz, J., Stemann, L., Sosik, H.M., et al., 2019. Globally consistent quantitative observations of planktonic ecosystems. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 6, 196. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00196>.
- Lorenzen, C.J., 1966. A method for the continuous measurement of in vivo chlorophyll concentration. *Deep-Sea Res.* 13. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0011-7471\(66\)91102-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0011-7471(66)91102-8).
- Marcarelli, A.M., Fulweiler, R.W., Scott, J.T., 2022. Nitrogen fixation: a poorly understood process along the freshwater-marine continuum. *Limnol. Ocean. Lett.* 7, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lo2.10220>.
- Matthews, M.W., Bernard, S., 2013. Using a two-layered sphere model to investigate the impact of gas vacuoles on the inherent optical properties of *Microcystis aeruginosa*. *Biogeosciences*. 10, 8139–8157. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-10-8139-2013>.
- McQuaid, N., Zamyadi, A., Prévost, M., Bird, D.F., Dörner, S., 2011. Use of in vivo phycocyanin fluorescence to monitor potential microcystin-producing cyanobacterial biovolume in a drinking water source. *J. Env. Monit.* 13, 455–463. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C0EM00163E>.
- Mirasbekov, Y., et al., 2021. Semi-automated classification of colonial *microcystis* by FlowCAM imaging flow cytometry in mesocosm experiment reveals high heterogeneity during seasonal bloom. *Sci. Rep.* 11, 9377. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-88661-2>.
- Moberg, E.A., Sosik, H.M., 2012. Distance maps to estimate cell volume from two-dimensional plankton images. *Limnol. Ocean. Methods* 10. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lom.2012.10.278>.
- Moldaenke, C., Fang, Y., Yang, F., Dahlhaus, A., 2019. Early warning method for cyanobacteria toxin, taste and odor problems by the evaluation of fluorescence signals. *Sci. Tot. Env.* 667. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.02.271>.
- Muller-Karger, F.E., Miloslavich, P., Bax, N.J., Simmons, S., Costello, M.J., Sousa Pinto, I., et al., 2018. Advancing marine biological observations and data requirements of the complementary essential ocean variables (EOVs) and essential biodiversity variables (EBVs) frameworks. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 5, 211. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2018.00211>.
- O’Neil, J.M., Davis, T.W., Burford, M.A., Gobler, C.J., 2012. The rise of harmful cyanobacteria blooms: the potential roles of eutrophication and climate change. *Harmful. Algae* 14, 313–334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2011.10.027>.
- Ogashawara, I., 2020. Determination of phycocyanin from space—A bibliometric analysis. *Remote Sens.* 12, 567. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12030567>.
- Olenina, I., Hajdu, S., Edler, L., Andersson, A., Wasmund, N., Busch, S., et al., 2006. Biovolumes and size-classes of phytoplankton in the Baltic Sea. *HELCOM. Balt. Sea Env. Proc.* 106. Annually updated appendix available at http://ices.dk/data/Documents/ENV/PEG_BVOL.zip.
- Olofsson, M., Suikkanen, S., Kobos, J., Wasmund, N., Karlson, B., 2020. Basin-specific changes in filamentous cyanobacteria community composition across four decades in the Baltic Sea. *Harmful. Algae* 91, 101685. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2019.101685>.
- Olson, R.J., Sosik, H.M., 2007. A submersible imaging-in-flow instrument to analyze nano- and micropikoplankton: imaging FlowCytobot. *Limnol. Ocean. Methods* 5, 195–203. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lom.2007.5.195>.
- Paerl, H.W., Otten, T.G., Kudela, R., 2018. Mitigating the expansion of harmful algal blooms across the freshwater-to-marine continuum. *Env. Sci. Technol.* 52, 5519–5529. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b05950>.
- Puillat, I., Farcy, P., Durand, D., Karlson, B., Petihakis, G., Seppälä, J., et al., 2016. Progress in marine science supported by European joint coastal observation systems: the JERICO-RI research infrastructure. *J. Mar. Syst.* 162, 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2016.06.004>.
- R Core Team, 2024. R: A language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Rantajarvi, E., Pitkänen, H., Korpinen, S., Nurmi, M., Ekebom, J., Liljaneni, P., et al., 2020. Manual for marine monitoring in Finland. Reports of the Finnish Environment Institute 47/2020. In: In Finnish and Swedish with English summary: Seuratakäsikirja Suomen merenhoitosuunnitelman seurantaohjelman vuosille 2020–2026. Suomen ympäristökeskuksen raportteja 47/2020. Suomen ympäristökeskus SYKE, p. 219 pages.
- Rome, M., Beighley, R.E., Faber, T., 2021. Sensor-based detection of algal blooms for public health advisories and long-term monitoring. *Sci. Tot. Env.* 767, 144984. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.144984>.
- Ruiz-Villarral, M., Sourisseau, M., Anderson, P., Cusack, C., Neira, P., Silke, J., et al., 2022. Novel methodologies for providing in situ data to HAB early warning systems in the European Atlantic area: the PRIMROSE experience. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 9, 791329. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.791329>.
- Sellner, K.G., 1997. Physiology, ecology, and toxic properties of marine cyanobacteria blooms. *Limnol. Ocean.* 42, 1089–1104. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lo.1997.42.5.1089>.
- Seppälä, J., Ylöstalo, P., Kaitala, S., Hällfors, S., Raateoja, M., Maunula, P., 2007. Ship-of-opportunity based phycocyanin fluorescence monitoring of the filamentous cyanobacteria bloom dynamics in the Baltic Sea. *Estuar. Coast. Shelf. Sci.* 73, 489–500. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eccs.2007.02.015>.
- Seppälä, J., Ylöstalo, P., Kuosa, H., 2005. Spectral absorption and fluorescence characteristics of phytoplankton in different size fractions across a salinity gradient in the Baltic Sea. *Int. J. Remote Sens.* 26, 387–414. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431160410001723682>.
- Sieracki, C.K., Sieracki, M.E., Yentsch, C.S., 1998. An imaging-in-flow system for automated analysis of marine microplankton. *Mar. Ecol. Progr. Ser.* 168, 285–296. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps168285>.
- Sonnet, V., Mouw, C.B., Ciochetto, A.B., Carney-Almeida, J., 2024. Hit or miss? Impact of time series resolution on resolving phytoplankton dynamics at hourly, weekly, and satellite remote sensing frequencies. *Limnol. Ocean. Methods.* <https://doi.org/10.1002/lom3.10604>.
- Stauffer, B.A., Bowers, H.A., Buckley, E., Davis, T.W., Johengen, T.H., Kudela, R., et al., 2019. Considerations in harmful algal bloom research and monitoring: perspectives from a consensus-building workshop and technology testing. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 6, 399. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00399>.
- Sun, J., Liu, D., 2003. Geometric models for calculating cell biovolume and surface area for phytoplankton. *J. Plankton Res.* 25, 1331–1346. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fgb096>.
- Thomson-Laing, G., Puddick, J., Wood, S.A., 2020. Predicting cyanobacterial biovolumes from phycocyanin fluorescence using a handheld fluorometer in the field. *Harmful. Algae* 97, 101869. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2020.101869>.
- Thyssen, M., Grégori, G., Créach, V., Lahbib, S., Dugenne, M., Aardema, H.M., et al., 2022. Interoperable vocabulary for marine microbial flow cytometry. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 9, 975877. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.975877>.
- Utermöhl, H., 1958. Methods of collecting plankton for various purposes are discussed. *SIL Commun.* 9, 1–38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/05384680.1958.11904091>.
- van Dijk, M.A., Gregori, G., Hoogveld, H.L., Rijkeboer, M., Denis, M., Malkasian, A., Gons, H.J., 2010. Optimizing the setup of a flow cytometric cell sorter for efficient quantitative sorting of long filamentous cyanobacteria. *Cytom. A* 77, 911–924. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cyto.a.20946>.
- Wasmund, N., 1997. Occurrence of cyanobacterial blooms in the Baltic Sea in relation to environmental conditions. *Int. Rev. Ges. Hydrobiol. Hydrogr.* 82, 169–184. <https://doi.org/10.1002/iroh.19970820205>.
- Watanabe, M., Ikeuchi, M., 2013. Phycobilisome: architecture of a light-harvesting supercomplex. *Photosynth. Res.* 116, 265–276. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s1120-013-9905-3>.
- Wells, M.L., Karlson, B., Wulff, A., Kudela, R., Trick, C., Asnaghi, V., et al., 2020. Future HAB science: directions and challenges in a changing climate. *Harmful. Algae* 91, 101632. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2019.101632>.
- Wickham, H., 2016. ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis. Springer-Verlag, New York. ISBN 978-3-319-24277-4. <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>.
- Yang, J., Holbach, A., Wilhelms, A., Qin, Y., Zheng, B., Zou, H., et al., 2019. Highly time-resolved analysis of seasonal water dynamics and algal kinetics based on in-situ multi-sensor-system monitoring data in Lake Taihu, China. *Sci. Env.* 660, 329–339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.01.044>.
- Zehr, J.P., Capone, D.G., 2020. Changing perspectives in marine nitrogen fixation. *Science* 368. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aay9514>.
- Ziegmann, M., Abert, M., Müller, M., Frimmel, F.H., 2010. Use of fluorescence fingerprints for the estimation of bloom formation and toxin production of *microcystis aeruginosa*. *Water. Res.* 44, 195–204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2009.09.035>.